

Environmental Pollution

A comprehensive experimental study of the influence of temperature on urban road traffic noise under real-world conditions --Manuscript Draft--

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Abstract:	<p>The effect of road traffic noise in urban environments is an issue of social and scientific interest, due to its public health and economic impacts. Scientific literature showed a decrease in the level of tyre/road noise generated as temperature increases, but usually under standardised traffic conditions in non-urban environments. Based on a wide network for the hourly monitoring of road traffic flow, air temperature and noise levels across the city of Madrid (Spain), this work proposes and applies a new experimental methodology for studying the dependence of urban road traffic noise on temperature. This study was conducted under real-world traffic conditions involving a wide variability in urban configurations and in the type and state of preservation of vehicles, tires and pavements. From the analysis of data for a whole year, a time interval was identified (from Tuesday to Thursday and between 8 a.m. and 8 p.m.) in which the variability in road traffic flow for the whole city of Madrid was stable enough to allow for a linear regression study between temperature and noise levels from urban road traffic. The relationships found were highly significant ($p \leq 0.001$) for data from all the noise monitoring stations, with values of higher than 20% and up to 42% for the explanation of the variability in the measured noise levels by temperature at most of the measurement points. The values of the slope coefficients at the noise monitoring stations ranged from -0.036 to -0.125 dB/°C, with an average value of -0.090 ± 0.011 dB/°C. These results are within the range of values reported in the scientific literature for experimental tests conducted under conditions of controlled or free-flowing traffic.</p>
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<p>Response to Reviewers:</p>	

HIGHLIGHTS

- A nominal range of ± 1.0 dB was found for 95% of the chosen hours at 54 gauge stations
- A method was found to study the link of urban road traffic noise with temperature
- The relationships were highly significant in the 21 noise monitoring stations used
- An average coefficient of -0.09 ± 0.01 dB/°C was obtained in the city of Madrid
- Advances were made in understanding the population's exposure to road traffic noise

Noise, traffic flow and temperature monitoring network

Variability of urban road traffic flow

Influence of temperature on urban road traffic noise

1 **A comprehensive experimental study of the influence of temperature**
2 **on urban road traffic noise under real-world conditions**

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12 **ABSTRACT**

13 The effect of road traffic noise in urban environments is an issue of social and
14 scientific interest, due to its public health and economic impacts. Scientific literature
15 showed a decrease in the level of tyre/road noise generated as temperature increases, but
16 usually under standardised traffic conditions in non-urban environments. Based on a wide
17 network for the hourly monitoring of road traffic flow, air temperature and noise levels
18 across the city of Madrid (Spain), this work proposes and applies a new experimental
19 methodology for studying the dependence of urban road traffic noise on temperature. This
20 study was conducted under real-world traffic conditions involving a wide variability in
21 urban configurations and in the type and state of preservation of vehicles, tires and
22 pavements. From the analysis of data for a whole year, a time interval was identified

23 (from Tuesday to Thursday and between 8 a.m. and 8 p.m.) in which the variability in
24 road traffic flow for the whole city of Madrid was stable enough to allow for a linear
25 regression study between temperature and noise levels from urban road traffic. The
26 relationships found were highly significant ($p \leq 0.001$) for data from all the noise
27 monitoring stations, with values of higher than 20% and up to 42% for the explanation of
28 the variability in the measured noise levels by temperature at most of the measurement
29 points. The values of the slope coefficients at the noise monitoring stations ranged from
30 -0.036 to -0.125 dB/°C, with an average value of -0.090 ± 0.011 dB/°C. These results
31 are within the range of values reported in the scientific literature for experimental tests
32 conducted under conditions of controlled or free-flowing traffic.

33 **Keywords:** road traffic noise; temperature correction; urban environments, long-
34 term measurements; noise mapping.

35 1. INTRODUCTION

36 Most of the world's population is nowadays concentrated in urban areas, so studies
37 have therefore been carried out to analyse the dependence of urban noise on the size of
38 these cities and their transport infrastructures (Zhao et al., 2022) (Barrigón Morillas et al.,
39 2021a). Relationships between different types of human health disorders or diseases and
40 noise pollution have been reported in the scientific literature (Andersson et al., 2020)
41 (Cantuaría et al., 2018) (Blume et al., 2022) (Hao et al., 2021). There are also associated
42 economic impacts of environmental noise in cities due to an increase in demand for health
43 care (Díaz et al., 2020) (Carmona et al., 2017) and the devaluation of housing located in
44 affected areas (Beimer and Maennig, 2017) (Szczepańska et al., 2015).

45 In general terms, the predominant source of environmental noise in urban contexts
46 is road traffic (EEA, 2020). Studies addressing the impacts of urban road traffic noise and

47 other associated problems are frequent in the scientific literature (Khan et al., 2020)
48 (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2021b) (Roswall et al., 2017) (Montes-González et al., 2019).
49 The contributions of tyre/road, engine and aerodynamic noise to the overall level of road
50 traffic noise can vary depending on several factors, such as the speed and type of the
51 vehicles, the characteristics of the tyres and road surfaces, and other conditions (IVT,
52 2005) (Vázquez et al., 2018) (Sandberg, U, 2003). And since temperature variations may
53 induce some changes in tyre stiffness and road surface porosity (Ling et al., 2021)
54 (Heutschi et al., 2016), the mechanisms of rolling noise generation can be influenced by
55 this variable. According to the Nord2000 method, rolling noise is predominant for light
56 and heavy vehicles driving at speeds above 40 km/h and 70 km/h, respectively (Kragh,
57 J., 2011). While the Swiss sonROAD18 model suggests an increased relevance of rolling
58 noise already from 30 km/h for passenger cars (Heutschi et al., 2018).

59 The influence of temperature on the generation of tyre/road noise has been
60 investigated in the scientific literature, mainly following the procedures established in
61 standards such as ISO 11819-1, ISO 11819-2 and ISO 11819-4 (ISO 11819-1, 1997) (ISO
62 11819-2, 2017) (ISO/PAS 11819-4, 2013), under controlled traffic conditions on roads
63 far from urban environments or in areas designated for this specific type of research.
64 These studies have shown a decrease in noise level as the environmental temperature
65 increases, with coefficients ranging between -0.03 and -0.11 dBA/°C (Yuan et al., 2019)
66 (Kneib et al., 2016) (Bueno et al., 2011) (Bühlmann et al., 2015) (Sandberg, U., 2015)
67 (Bühlmann and Ziegler, 2011) (Anfosso-LédéE and Pichaud, 2007). A correction for
68 temperature when testing with the CPX method (ISO 11819-2, 2017) is proposed in the
69 ISO/TS 13471-1:2017 standard (ISO/TS 13471-1, 2017) that varies between -0.04 and
70 -0.11 dBA/°C, but this is only valid for two specific types of tyre, and is not applicable
71 to a general circulation fleet. A recent study based on the CPX method proposed to

72 combine the variables of air and road temperature in the correction approaches for
73 temperature to ensure that important influences on tyre/road noise such as solar radiation
74 and ambient air are taken into account (Bühlmann et al., 2021). There has also been
75 research on the relationship between road traffic noise level and temperature under
76 conditions of uncontrolled traffic flow (the type of vehicles and tyres used in the
77 measurements is not decided, as neither is controlled their state of preservation). Jabben
78 (Jabben, J., 2013) conducted a study under free-flowing traffic conditions in which the
79 maximum sound pressure level (L_{Amax}) of each individual vehicle was recorded, as
80 indicated in the ISO 11819-1 standard (ISO 11819-1, 1997). A negative increase in the
81 coefficient of between -0.03 and -0.12 dBA/°C was obtained for passenger vehicles and
82 speeds of between 50 and 140 km/h, while a value of -0.04 dB/°C was found for
83 middleweight trucks in the range 70–100 km/h. Another study conducted under free
84 flowing road traffic conditions was recently published by Sanchez-Fernández et al.
85 (Sánchez-Fernández et al., 2021). Broadband results showed a variation in the road traffic
86 noise level with a coefficient of -0.161 ± 0.020 dBA/°C for air temperature and -0.058
87 ± 0.007 dBA/°C for pavement temperature, considering the equivalent sound level (L_{Aeq})
88 obtained from measurements with a minimum of 100 vehicles passing. In connection with
89 this issue, the European Directive 996/2015 (COM, 2015) introduced the Common Noise
90 Assessment Methods in Europe (CNOSSOS-EU) for the standardisation of strategic noise
91 mapping calculations in European countries. The CNOSSOS-EU method makes a
92 correction to the sound power emitted by road traffic to take into account the reduction
93 in noise as air temperature rises, with coefficients of -0.08 dB/°C for light vehicles
94 (category 1) and -0.04 dB/°C for heavy vehicles (categories 2 and 3). Kragh et al. (Kragh,
95 J. et al., 2006) have also proposed a correction to the predicted noise level as a function
96 of air temperature for the Nord2000 method (Nord2000, 2006), with a negative slope

97 varying according to the type of road surface (dense asphalt concrete or stone mastic
98 asphalt).

99 Studies of road traffic noise in urban environments have focused on methodological
100 aspects such as spatial sampling (Quintero et al., 2021) (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2011)
101 (Romeu et al., 2011), temporal sampling (Huang et al., 2021) (Montes González et al.,
102 2020a) (Prieto Gajardo et al., 2016), the urban and architectural characteristics of the
103 streets (Forssén et al., 2022) (Montes González et al., 2020b), the positions of the
104 microphones (Zagubień and Wolniewicz, 2021) (Montes González et al., 2020c) (Mateus
105 et al., 2015) and noise modelling (Aumond et al., 2021) (Rey Gozalo et al., 2019)
106 (Nascimento et al., 2021). Also, the study of traffic noise can be improved with more
107 details about traffic flow detection (Fredianelli et al., 2022). However, studies analysing
108 the relationship between noise level from road traffic and air temperature under real traffic
109 conditions in urban environments are rare. Only a previous study, estimating long-term
110 noise level by short-term measurements, has found that average annual temperature was
111 significantly related with road traffic noise at 31.5 Hz and 63 Hz, but not with $L_{Aeq,24h}$
112 (Wang et al., 2016). Conducting this type of research in real traffic conditions and in
113 different urban scenarios would greatly expand the framework of study of this
114 dependency. In contrast to previous research, situations with a wide variability in the
115 range of aspects such as the vehicle brands and models and their state of maintenance, the
116 tire types and their state of conservation, the urban settings and the types and age of road
117 surfaces are considered simultaneously for the first time. Some urban traffic conditions
118 may differ from those of non-urban transport infrastructures, as well as the speed range
119 or the percentage of heavy vehicles, which are generally lower in cities. This work
120 proposes and applies a methodology for studying the dependence of the noise level
121 generated by urban road traffic on temperature, under real-world traffic conditions in a

122 large city (Madrid, Spain). For achieve this objective, long-term measurements with an
123 integration period of one hour were carried out at different points in the city to monitor
124 the equivalent sound level (L_{Aeq}), traffic flow and temperature. To the best of the authors'
125 knowledge, this is the first time that an experimental methodology has been proposed to
126 achieve this objective.

127 **2. MATERIALS AND METHODS**

128 **2.1. Study area and data collection**

129 The study was carried out in the city of Madrid (Spain), that covers an area of
130 605.77 km² and an it has an official population of 3,334,730 people (INE, 2020), although
131 the extended metropolitan area has 6,779,888 inhabitants. In addition to the main avenues
132 and streets, the road transport infrastructure of Madrid consists of a series of ring roads
133 for the redistribution of traffic flow, and the city is located at the centre of a radial
134 transport system that connects it with the rest of Spain through six main highways and
135 other secondary highways and roads (Fig. 1a). In terms of weather conditions, there is
136 usually a large variation in both temperature (with average temperature oscillations
137 ranging between 3 and 25°C) and humidity, depending on the season (AEMET, 2021).
138 Annual rainfall is around 400 mm, and the average annual wind speed is between 7 and
139 10 km/h (AEMET, 2021).

140 The city of Madrid has a wide network of devices for the continuous monitoring of
141 different variables related to the management of urban traffic and environmental
142 conditions in the city (Ayuntamiento de Madrid, 2021). In particular, there are 60 fixed
143 stations throughout the city to measure the flow of road traffic, 31 stations for monitoring
144 noise levels, and 22 stations for taking readings of meteorological variables and air quality
145 (see Fig. 1b). A knowledge of the traffic flows, noise levels, levels of particulate matter

146 and chemical pollutants, and weather conditions allows for predictions of the possible
147 effects on citizens. Fig. 1b shows the distribution of the noise (green), temperature (red)
148 and traffic flow (blue) measurement points in Madrid.

149

150 Fig. 1. (a) Overview of the road transport infrastructure of Madrid; (b) distributions of
151 the noise, temperature and traffic flow measurement points in the study area; (c, d)
152 locations of some microphones (from Google Street View)

153 When carrying out this study, all the data from the year 2019 collected from the
154 networks for measuring vehicle flow, noise levels and meteorological variables were
155 processed as described below.

156 2.2. Measurement procedure

157 The noise level measurement network consists of 31 stations located throughout the
158 city (Fig. 1b). *In situ* measurements of the equivalent sound level (L_{Aeq}) were carried out
159 using a logging period of 1 hour. Class 1 measuring stations (IEC 61672-1, 2013) were

160 used, whose microphones were placed in the vicinity of traffic lanes and at heights of
161 approximately 4 to 6 metres above the ground, trying to avoid reflections on nearby
162 surfaces (ISO 1996-2, 2017) (Montes Gonzalez et al., 2018). Fig.1c and Fig.1d show the
163 locations of microphones at some of the measurement points.

164 In view of the objective of this work, also hourly monitored data of vehicle flow
165 (60 stations) and temperature (22 stations) were used (Fig. 1b). Vehicle flow data were
166 used in order to determine the flow variability and to identify whether certain time
167 intervals existed in which vehicle flow could be considered stable enough to obtain a
168 theoretical maximum range of variability of noise associated to traffic variability. For this
169 study a range of ± 1.0 dB was considered. This theoretical range implies a variation of
170 $\pm 26\%$ in traffic flow ($a = 1.26$ in Eq.(1)). Since the variability in the noise level is
171 reduced if time periods of longer than one hour or the median value for the different
172 stations are employed, a more restrictive range was estimated to be adequate in these
173 cases. To this end, the range of ± 0.5 dB was considered. That implied a theoretical
174 variation of $\pm 12\%$ in traffic flow ($a = 1.12$ in Eq.(1)).

175
$$Lw' = Lw + 10 \log(a) \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

176 where $w' = a \cdot w$

177 Some criteria were applied to discard measuring stations and anomalous data. When
178 the main sound source in the noise monitoring station environment was not road traffic
179 noise, it was not considered. It was discarded that a station should be discarded from the
180 analysis if the data loss exceeded 10% of the hours. Concerning the presence of anomalies
181 in the sound profiles, it was considered that, in cases where they occupied less than 10%
182 of the measurement time, this time period would be eliminated from the analysis; if they
183 exceeded 10%, the station would be discarded. Logically, also all sound events that varied
184 by more than 10 dB from the average were excluded.

185 **2.3. Statistical Analyses**

186 A linear regression analysis was performed to analyse the relationship between
187 $L_{Aeq,1h}$ (dB) and temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) at each measurement station. The coefficient of
188 determination (R^2) and the standard error of the coefficients were also calculated. The F -
189 test was used to determine the significance of the relationship between both variables.
190 The overall average slope and its 95% confidence interval were determined from the slope
191 values obtained for each monitoring station. The standard deviation and the t student
192 distribution were used for the calculation of the confidence interval because the number
193 of monitoring stations selected was 21. Matlab R2021b was used for the above analyses.

194 **3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

195 **3.1. Analysis of vehicle flow stability**

196 The aim of this section is to identify whether there are time periods in which the
197 flow of road traffic in the city has a high enough value and sufficient stability to allow
198 the effect of traffic flow on the variability in sound levels to be delimited. To achieve the
199 highest possible temporal accuracy, the same interval of integration of the recording
200 devices (one hour) was used as the basis for the flow analysis, although the usefulness of
201 other time intervals of longer duration could also be explored. Although the noise
202 pollution monitoring network points were located at different points from those of the
203 flow gauging network, it is logical to assume that if such a stable time period existed for
204 all or most of the traffic flow gauging stations, it could be considered valid for the whole
205 city. During this period, as long as the predominant source of noise was road traffic, the
206 variability in the sound levels should be explained by the variation in temperature in a
207 statistically significant way.

208 3.1.1. Preliminary analysis

209 First, graphical analyses of the annual evolution of the flow were carried out based
210 on time intervals of hours and days, as can be seen in the example of a station shown in
211 Fig. a of Supplementary Material. From these graphical analyses of all the stations, it was
212 observed that the data from six stations had total or partial absences or anomalies in the
213 measurements, and these were therefore discarded from the study. At the remaining 54
214 stations, the average hourly flow for all stations (54·8760 one-hour slots) over 2019 was
215 1655 veh/h, with a minimum value of 259 veh/h at one station. From an analysis of these
216 stations, it was possible to observe the expected weekly variation in the road traffic, with
217 daily variations, reductions at weekends, and a decrease in flow around the summer
218 holiday period. This graphical analysis also allowed some temporary periods to be
219 detected in which there was an unexpected drop in the flow values at most of the stations.
220 This decrease seemed to be associated with weekly periods and therefore a detailed study
221 of the weekly flow has been carried out in the following section.

222 3.1.2. Weekly flow analysis

223 When the preliminary analysis was complete, a study of the variability in the
224 average weekly vehicle flow was carried out. For this, the data from the 54 correctly
225 operating flow stations were used. Logically, each station had vehicle flow values that
226 were not comparable between them, so it was necessary to normalise the flows. To this
227 end, the ratio of the vehicle flow for each week with respect to the annual average value
228 of the weeks was calculated for each flow gauging station. In this way, the data from all
229 the stations could be compared and used together. These ratios were then averaged over
230 54 stations, giving a single ratio for each of week of the year and for the whole city of
231 Madrid. A graphical representation of the results obtained for the averaged ratio of

232 normalised road traffic flow from all the 54 stations for each week of the year is shown
233 in Fig. b of Supplementary Material with red star markers.

234 Based on these values, a sequential analysis was carried out of the weeks in which
235 the ratio of vehicle flow exceeded the 12% variability range with respect to the annual
236 mean. In each phase, those weeks with flows exceeding this range of variability were
237 eliminated and the mean was recalculated. As a result of this process, data for all the
238 weeks corresponding to the month of August and all those which had two or more bank
239 holidays in the city of Madrid in 2019 were finally discarded. All the remaining weeks (a
240 total of 44) had a ratio of the vehicle flow within the range of 12% with respect to the
241 average of those weeks. This implies that the expected variability associated with traffic
242 at weekly levels is ± 0.5 dB. The results are shown in Fig. b of Supplementary Material
243 with blue circle markers.

244 3.1.3 Analysis of the stability period

245 For all flow gauging stations, using data from the weeks that met the stability
246 criterion set out above, an analysis was made of the evolution of the hourly flow, for each
247 day of the week. The aim was to see if there was any time period during the year in which
248 the variability of the flow, using the minimum interval of the logging network (one hour),
249 could meet the stability criterion of 26%. For this purpose, the flow for each hour of the
250 year at each station ($365 \cdot 24 = 8760$ hours) was normalised with respect to the annual
251 flow, and these data were then averaged for each day of the week (Monday to Sunday),
252 resulting in 168 values for each station. Finally, the hourly results for all 54 flow
253 measurement stations were averaged. The results of this analysis are shown in Fig. 2.

254

255 Fig. 2. Average ratio of normalised road traffic flow from all stations, for each day of
 256 the week

257 Fig. 2 shows that Saturdays and Sundays had notable differences in flow compared
 258 to working days. Although a certain stability can be observed for all weekdays, on closer
 259 inspection, Fridays show a different time structure. It can also be noted that the greatest
 260 stability and similarity in behaviour occurs from Monday to Thursday, in the period
 261 between 8 a.m. and 8 p.m., where Mondays have a slightly lower flow values than the
 262 other three days. Based on these preliminary results for weekly traffic flow, it can be
 263 concluded that there seems to be an enough stability of flows in the daily interval from
 264 Tuesday to Thursday and during the hourly period from 8 a.m. to 8 p.m (36 hours). This
 265 potential stability was then analysed further.

266 Therefore, in order to analyse this preliminary conclusion in detail, the ratio of
 267 hours between Tuesday and Thursday and during the period 8 a.m. to 8 p.m. with a flow
 268 variation of 26% with respect to the annual average (1560 hours) was calculated for each
 269 of the 54 gauging stations. The mean ratio of hours was then determined for all the
 270 stations. The results indicated that on average, more than 95% of the hourly time slots

271 (1482 of 1560 hours) met the 26% requirement considering all stations. And individually,
272 more than 72% of the stations (39 stations) have more than 95% of the hours (1482 of
273 1560 hours) verifying the requirement for 26% flow variability. The gauging station with
274 the lowest ratio in this range had 77% of the hours (1201 hours) verifying this
275 requirement. In conclusion, taking into account the hour as the base time interval of
276 calculation, the fact that there was a time interval (from Tuesday to Thursday and from 8
277 a.m. to 8 p.m.) in which the variability of the flow is less than 26% of the average flow
278 for more than 95% of the hours, corresponding to 54 traffic gauging stations in a large
279 city such as Madrid, can be considered an important result that allows for a linear
280 regression study between environmental temperature and the noise levels measured in
281 this time interval. The avenues and streets of Madrid where the monitoring stations were
282 located belonged to urban roads where the speed limit in 2019 was 50 km/h.

283 **3.2. Analysis of the annual variability in temperature**

284 The temperature measurement network is composed of 22 stations, which are
285 generally placed at different locations from those for measuring sound levels. Given this
286 lack of coincidence between the measuring stations for both variables of interest, in order
287 to carry out a study of the dependence of the sound level on temperature, a prior study of
288 the temperature data measured at the different stations was carried out in order to verify
289 their correct functioning and to check that similar trends were seen at all points. The
290 average value for all stations could then be used for the linear regression analysis.

291 This preliminary graphical analysis of all stations showed some anomalies. In
292 particular, one of the stations had a significant lack of data, and was therefore discarded
293 from the analysis. It was also observed that there were occasional data losses at a relevant
294 proportion of the stations (19 stations). An example is given in Fig. c of Supplementary

295 Material. These partial data were discarded, while the rest of the data at these stations
296 were retained.

297 Once the data were verified, an analysis of the annual variability was carried out
298 and similar trends were found for all stations. Fig. d of Supplementary Material shows
299 the average temperature at the 21 monitoring stations for each day of the year, as well as
300 the values of the maximum and minimum temperatures measured in the temperature
301 network. Given the evolution of the mean, maximum and minimum temperature values
302 throughout the year (Fig. d of Supplementary Material), it can be concluded that the
303 structure of the annual variation is similar in the different measuring stations. Therefore,
304 it was considered that the mean temperature, taken from the data from the 21 temperature
305 measurement stations spread throughout the city, can be considered representative of the
306 hourly variation at all of the sound measurement points.

307 **3.3. Analysis of the dependence of road traffic noise level on temperature**

308 As a result of the study of the temporal variability in road traffic flow over a large
309 urban area, based on data from 54 traffic gauging stations, a time interval was found in
310 which more than 95% of the hourly time slots deviated less than 26% from the average
311 flow. If the main source of sound at these noise level measurement points is road traffic,
312 this average variability in flow would be equivalent to an average variability in noise
313 levels of 1 dBA. Consequently, an analysis of the noise pollution measurement network
314 should be carried out to detect those stations where other noise sources may be
315 predominant or where, for different reasons, there may be a lack of data or a significant
316 presence of anomalous events. This was done by means of two simultaneous procedures:
317 the location of each station was examined in order to estimate the foreseeable sources of
318 noise in the area; and a graphical representation of the annual variability was created in

319 order to determine the variability in noise levels at each station and to detect possible
320 absences of data, alterations in their usual operation or the presence and importance of
321 anomalous noise events (Fig. e of Supplementary Material). Since the distances between
322 the nearest street (centre of the traffic lines) and the measurement microphone in range
323 from 10 m to 35 m for the measurement stations used in this study, the variation of sound
324 absorption as a function of weather conditions is not considered in the study (ISO 1996-
325 2; IEC 61672-1:2013).

326 The previously described criteria were considered for discarding measurement
327 stations and anomalous data. From the analysis of the locations of these stations, it was
328 concluded that road traffic was not the main source of noise at three of them: stations 3,
329 18 and 26. Station 3 was located in a square with restricted traffic and significant
330 commercial activity, whereas station 18 was situated in a large green area, and station 26
331 was near a set of suburban train tracks with a significant flow of rail traffic. From an
332 examination of the annual sound profiles, anomalous events and data loss were found at
333 all the 31 stations, randomly throughout the year, both in a punctual manner and in certain
334 longer periods of time. As the data loss exceeded 10% of the 8760 hours ($365 \cdot 24$) in the
335 stations 11, 12, 16 and 28, they were discarded from the analysis. The stations 14, 15 and
336 17 were eliminated because the anomalous periods exceeded 10% of the measurement
337 time. The anomalous periods in the sound profiles that occupied less than 10% were
338 discarded from the analysis in stations 1, 4, 5, 20 and 24. As an example, Fig. f is included
339 in the Supplementary Material that shows the annual sound profile for station 5, with an
340 integration period of one hour. In this figure, it can be seen that around hours 4,000 and
341 6,800, there were continuous sound levels which exceed the base period (day (7:00-
342 19:00), evening (19:00-23:00) and night (23:00-07:00)) value by more than 10 and 20
343 dB, respectively. Logically, also all sound events that varied by more than 10 dB from

344 the average were excluded. Finally, 21 of the 31 stations that comprise the noise pollution
 345 measurement network were used for this study of the relationship between noise levels
 346 and environmental temperature (Fig. e of Supplementary Material).

347 Table 1 shows the values of the different parameters of the regression analysis between
 348 road traffic noise levels and temperature in the areas of Madrid where the noise
 349 monitoring stations were located. The values of the slope (with standard error), intercept
 350 coefficient, coefficient of determination (R^2), significance level and number of data (N)
 351 are given. As an example of the analysis performed to obtain the results shown in Table
 352 1, Fig. 3 shows the measured values of the hourly equivalent sound level over one year
 353 with respect to temperature at two monitoring stations in Madrid.

354 Table 1. Parameters used in the regression analysis between road traffic noise levels
 355 ($L_{Aeq,1h}$) and temperature in the different areas of Madrid (from Tuesday to Thursday and
 356 from 8 a.m. to 8 p.m.)

Nº	Station name	Slope (Std. Error)	Intercept coefficient	R^2	Sig.	N
1	Paseo de Recoletos	-0.069 (0.004)	69.2	0.23	≤ 0.001	1246
2	Carlos V	-0.059 (0.004)	71.1	0.15	≤ 0.001	1515
4	Plaza de España	-0.104 (0.005)	66.4	0.24	≤ 0.001	1152
5	Barrio del Pilar	-0.055 (0.005)	62.4	0.08	≤ 0.001	1507
6	Gregorio Marañón	-0.080 (0.002)	73.6	0.42	≤ 0.001	1482
7	Escuelas Aguirres	-0.073 (0.003)	68.5	0.24	≤ 0.001	1478
8	Cuatro Caminos	-0.092 (0.004)	67.8	0.23	≤ 0.001	1452
9	Ramón y Cajal	-0.098 (0.004)	70.8	0.28	≤ 0.001	1499
10	Manuel Becerra	-0.036 (0.005)	65.1	0.04	≤ 0.001	1515
13	Arturo Soria	-0.125 (0.004)	64.4	0.36	≤ 0.001	1497
19	Santa Eugenia	-0.084 (0.004)	68.6	0.26	≤ 0.001	1520
20	Embajada	-0.107 (0.005)	63.6	0.26	≤ 0.001	1530
21	Barajas Pueblo	-0.120 (0.004)	64.6	0.42	≤ 0.001	1478
22	Cuatro vientos	-0.113 (0.004)	70.3	0.39	≤ 0.001	1486
23	El Pardo	-0.063 (0.005)	59.0	0.08	≤ 0.001	1505
24	Campo de las Naciones	-0.091 (0.005)	62.6	0.20	≤ 0.001	1473
25	Sanchinarro	-0.116 (0.005)	65.5	0.30	≤ 0.001	1451
27	Castellana	-0.096 (0.003)	65.3	0.37	≤ 0.001	1512

29	Ensanche de Vallecas	-0.123 (0.004)	63.4	0.38	≤ 0.001	1518
30	Urb. Emabajada II	-0.102 (0.005)	59.0	0.21	≤ 0.001	1529
31	Tres Olivos	-0.080 (0.005)	60.1	0.16	≤ 0.001	1519

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358

359 Fig. 3. Values of L_{Aeq} measured every hour over a period of one year with respect to
 360 temperature at (a) station 20; (b) station 21

361 The relationships shown in Table 1 between urban road traffic noise levels and
 362 temperature were highly significant ($p \leq 0.001$) for all the monitoring stations located in
 363 Madrid. The values for the explanation of the variability in the measured noise levels by
 364 temperature were higher than 20% at most measurement points, and values of 42% were
 365 reached at some of them. These results can be considered noteworthy because they
 366 indicate that a significant ratio of the variability in urban road traffic noise can be
 367 predicted based only on the average temperature when the traffic flow is stable. The
 368 relationships obtained are independent of the time period considered in the study and are
 369 valid for day-time period or a night-time period, for a working day or a public holiday,
 370 given the nature of the physical mechanisms involved. Values of between 4% and 8% for

371 the explanation of variability were obtained at three of the monitoring stations, and these
372 could be associated with the presence of noise sources other than urban road traffic in
373 their environments. All the results were obtained by applying a relatively unrestrictive
374 criterion of eliminating anomalous sound events when the sound level varied by more
375 than 10 dB with respect to the annual average for each station. Since the equivalent sound
376 level recorded over one hour at a given point does not show much variability when the
377 main sound source is road traffic (for a stable vehicle flow), other more restrictive criteria
378 for the elimination of anomalous sound events could be applied meaning that higher
379 values for the explanation of the variability in the noise level with temperature would be
380 obtained at all measurement stations, with the same sign for the slope. A previous study
381 conducted in Taichung (Taiwan) did not find a significant relationship between average
382 annual road traffic noise ($L_{Aeq,24h}$) and temperature, although a significant negative
383 relationship between average annual temperature and traffic noise in the 31.5 Hz and 63
384 Hz octave bands was reported (Wang et al., 2016). These results are probably related to
385 the use of a 24-hour noise indicator and the fact that road traffic flow in cities usually
386 decreases considerably during the night and is not the main source of noise during this
387 period.

388 It can also be noted from Table 1 that all slope coefficients are negative, indicating
389 a negative dependence of the road traffic noise level on temperature. The slope coefficient
390 values obtained at the 21 noise monitoring stations range from -0.036 to -0.125 dB/°C.
391 These results are within the range of values reported in the scientific literature (Yuan et
392 al., 2019) (Kneib et al., 2016) (Bueno et al., 2011) (Bühlmann et al., 2015) (Sandberg, U.,
393 2015) (Bühlmann and Ziegler, 2011) (Anfosso-LédéE and Pichaud, 2007) (Bühlmann et
394 al., 2021) (Sánchez-Fernández et al., 2021) (Jabben, J., 2013). Different results have been

395 reported for the speed dependency of temperature effects in the literature (Bühlmann et
396 al., 2015). The results presented for tyre/road noise from tests undertaken only under
397 controlled conditions differ in terms of whether the coefficient of variation of sound level
398 with temperature decreases or increases as vehicle speed rises (Bühlmann et al., 2015).
399 On the other hand, the results obtained for road traffic in free flowing traffic conditions
400 show higher temperature effects at higher speeds (Jabben, J., 2013). Since the scientific
401 literature shows highly significant relationships between air and pavement temperature
402 with high values of the coefficient of determination (Anfosso-LédéE and Pichaud, 2007)
403 (Sánchez-Fernández et al., 2021), similar results could probably be achieved in the case
404 that pavement temperature could have been monitored. If it is considered that the general
405 speed limit established for urban environments in Madrid was 50 km/h on the dates when
406 the measurements were taken, the values obtained at many of the monitoring stations (see
407 Table 1) in Madrid were higher than those previously reported in the scientific literature
408 under free traffic flow conditions at this speed (Jabben, J., 2013), and are more similar to
409 those reported for controlled traffic conditions (Bühlmann et al., 2015) (Bueno et al.,
410 2011).

411 In the case of the calculation methods for strategic noise maps, the CNOSSOS-EU
412 method (COM, 2015) proposes a correction of -0.08 dB/°C for light vehicles and -0.04
413 dB/°C for heavy vehicles, while the Nord2000 method (Kragh, J. et al., 2006) suggests
414 coefficients of -0.1 dB/°C and -0.062 dB/°C for dense asphalt concrete and stone mastic
415 asphalt, respectively. No dependence on vehicle speed was established. When the values
416 of the slope coefficients shown in Table 1 for all noise monitoring stations in Madrid are
417 averaged, a value of -0.090 ± 0.011 dB/°C (95% confidence interval) is found, which

418 would be within the range provided by both the CNOSSOS-EU method (COM, 2015) for
419 light vehicles and the Nord2000 method (Kragh, J. et al., 2006).

420 **4. CONCLUSIONS**

421 This experimental research proposes a novel methodology for studying the
422 dependence on temperature of the noise level generated by urban road traffic under real-
423 world traffic conditions. Highly significant ($p \leq 0.001$) relationships were found between
424 urban road traffic noise levels and temperature in the period of stable traffic flow (from
425 Tuesday to Thursday and from 8 a.m. to 8 p.m.) for all the noise monitoring stations
426 located in the city of Madrid. The explanation of the variability of measured noise levels
427 by temperature was over 20% at most of the measurement points, and values of up to 42%
428 were reached at some of them. The values of the slope coefficients obtained at the noise
429 monitoring stations ranged from -0.04 to -0.13 dB/°C. When the values of the slope
430 coefficients were averaged for all noise monitoring stations in order to compare them with
431 the corrections proposed for strategic noise mapping, it was found a value of $-0.090 \pm$
432 0.011 dB/°C (95% confidence interval).

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639

Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

CRediT author statement

Juan Miguel Barrigón Morillas: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Resources, Data Curation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Guillermo Rey-Gozalo:** Software, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data Curation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualization, Funding acquisition. **David Montes González:** Investigation, Data Curation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualization. **Manuel Sánchez-Fernández:** Investigation, Writing - Review & Editing. **Alicia Bachiller León:** Software, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data Curation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualization.